

Finite faithful G -sets are asymptotically free

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Let G be a finite nontrivial group, let X be a finite faithful G -set, let $P^i X$ be the i -th power set of X , let $n(i)$ be the number of points of $P^i X$, let $m(i)$ be the number of points of $P^i X$ with non-trivial stabilizer, let k be the number of prime order subgroups of G , and set $E(j) := 2^j$ for any integer j . We prove $\frac{n(i)}{m(i)} \geq \frac{1}{k} E\left(\frac{n(i-1)}{4}\right)$ for $i \geq 2$.

Let G be a finite nontrivial group, X a finite faithful G -set, write PX for the power set of X , define the sets $P^i X$ for $i \in \mathbb{N}$ by $P^0 X = X$ and $P^{i+1} X = PP^i X$, let $n(i)$ be the number of points in $P^i X$, let $M(i)$ be the set of all $\xi \in P^i X$ such that there is a $g \in G$ satisfying $g \neq 1$ and $g\xi = \xi$, let $m(i)$ be the number of points of $M(i)$, and set $E(j) := 2^j$ for any integer j .

We expect the sequence

$$\frac{n(1)}{m(1)}, \frac{n(2)}{m(2)}, \dots$$

to grow explosively. Let us illustrate this with the toy example where G and X have cardinality two. We get

$$\frac{n(1)}{m(1)} = \frac{4}{2} = 2, \quad \frac{n(2)}{m(2)} = \frac{16}{8} = 2, \quad \frac{n(3)}{m(3)} = \frac{E(16)}{E(12)} = 16,$$

$$\frac{n(4)}{m(4)} = \frac{E(E(16))}{E(E(15) + E(11))} = E(15 E(11)),$$

and $\frac{n(4)}{m(4)}$ turns out to have 9248 digits.

The purpose of this text is to try to shed some light on this phenomenon.

Theorem. *Let G be a finite nontrivial group and X a finite faithful G -set, and i an integer ≥ 2 . Then, in the above setting, we have*

$$\frac{n(i)}{m(i)} \geq \frac{1}{k} E\left(\frac{n(i-1)}{4}\right) = \frac{1}{k} E\left(E(n(i-2) - 2)\right),$$

where k is the number of prime order subgroups of G .

Proposition 1. *Let G be a group acting on a set Y with finitely many orbits. Then G has precisely 2^r fixed points in PY , where r is the number of G -orbits in Y .*

Proof. The fixed points in PY are the invariant subsets of Y , which are unions of G -orbits. \square

Recall that $n(i)$ is the cardinality of $P^i X$, so that we have $n(i+1) = E(n(i))$ for all i .

We start by assuming that the order of G is a prime number p ; in particular $m(i)$ is the number of fixed points of G in $P^i X$.

Proposition 2. *We have, in the above setting,*

$$\frac{n(i)}{m(i)} \geq E\left(\frac{n(i-1)}{4}\right)$$

for all $i \geq 2$.

Proof. Let $r(i)$ be the number of G -orbits in $P^i X$, and $f(i)$ the number of free G -orbits (that is, of orbits with p points) in $P^i X$.

Let i be a nonnegative integer. We have

$$\begin{cases} n(i) = pf(i) + m(i) \\ r(i) = f(i) + m(i). \end{cases}$$

Let us express $f(i)$ and $r(i)$ in term of $n(i)$ and $m(i)$:

$$f(i) = \frac{n(i) - m(i)}{p},$$

$$r(i) = \frac{n(i) + (p-1)m(i)}{p}.$$

In view of the equalities

$$n(i+1) = E(n(i)), \quad m(i+1) = E(r(i))$$

(Proposition 1), we get

$$m(i+1) = E\left(\frac{n(i) + (p-1)m(i)}{p}\right),$$

$$\frac{n(i+1)}{m(i+1)} = E\left(\frac{p-1}{p} (n(i) - m(i))\right) = E((p-1)f(i)) \geq 2,$$

the inequality $f(i) \geq 1$ following from our faithfulness assumption. This is easily seen to imply

$$n(i) - m(i) \geq \frac{n(i)}{2} \quad \forall i \geq 1,$$

so that we get for $i \geq 2$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{n(i)}{m(i)} &= E \left(\frac{p-1}{p} (n(i-1) - m(i-1)) \right) \\ &\geq E \left(\frac{p-1}{2p} n(i-1) \right) \geq E \left(\frac{n(i-1)}{4} \right). \end{aligned}$$

□

Proof of the Theorem. We know that the Theorem is true of G has prime order. Let us show that the Theorem holds for any finite group G .

Let \mathcal{H} be the set of prime order subgroups of G . For each subgroup H of G let $M(i, H)$ be the set of all $\xi \in P^i X$ such that there is a $h \in H$ satisfying $h \neq 1$ and $h\xi = \xi$, and write $m(i, H)$ for the cardinality of $M(i, H)$. We get $M(i, G) = M(i)$,

$$M(i) = \bigcup_{H \in \mathcal{H}} M(i, H), \quad m(i) \leq \sum_{H \in \mathcal{H}} m(i, H),$$

and, for $i \geq 2$,

$$\frac{m(i)}{n(i)} \leq \sum_{H \in \mathcal{H}} E \left(\frac{n(i-1)}{4} \right)^{-1} = k E \left(\frac{n(i-1)}{4} \right)^{-1},$$

where k is the cardinality of \mathcal{H} .

□

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